

The Complexity of the Old English Term Úhta: Meaning and Symbolism in “The Wanderer”

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RESUMEN : El presente artículo analiza la palabra del inglés antiguo *úhta*, prestando especial atención tanto a su configuración lingüística como a su función literaria en el conocido poema *The Wanderer*. En primera instancia, se realiza un examen detallado de sus propiedades fonológicas y morfológicas, seguido de un estudio de su evolución semántica y su desaparición del léxico inglés. A continuación, se aborda la contribución temática y simbólica de *úhta* en *The Wanderer*, especialmente en relación con las concepciones cristianas de luz, oscuridad y despertar espiritual.

Palabras clave: inglés antiguo, *úhta*, *The Wanderer*, evolución semántica, simbolismo, imagería cristiana.

ABSTRACT: This paper explores the Old English word *úhta*, focusing on both its linguistic form and literary function in the well-known poem, *The Wanderer*. It begins with an analysis of the word's phonological and morphological features, followed by its semantic development and eventual disappearance from the English language. The study then moves to examine how *úhta* contributes thematically and symbolically to *The Wanderer*, particularly in relation to Christian notions of light, darkness, and spiritual awakening.

Keywords: Old English, *úhta*, *The Wanderer*, semantic evolution, symbolism, Christian imagery.

‘So the darkness shall be the light, /
and the stillness the dancing’¹

The Old English (OE) term *úhta* is the focus of this study. It begins with an examination of its formal aspects and proceeds to scrutinize its usage and deeper connotations within the poem *The Wanderer*.

Úhta is a masculine noun², although it is irregular in gender and can occasionally appear as feminine. It also has a strong form, *úht*, which probably became an accepted variant due to its frequent use as the initial element in compound words. Additionally, it might be phonetically transcribed as /¹u:xtə³ and begins with a long vowel sound /u:/ similar to the vowel in the modern English (ME) word *fool*⁴; for this reason, in printing OE texts this <u> is usually marked with a macron <ū>⁵. After the vowel, we find the consonant /x/ which appears in the modern German word *nacht*, then, the consonant /t/ follows, like the one in the ME word *tail*⁶ and, finally, the vowel sound that resembles the sound /ə/ in ME. In terms of spelling evolution, we cannot state much because *úhta* was lost around the 15th century. As evidenced

¹ T.S. Eliot, ‘East Coker’, in *Four Quarters* (London: Faber and Faber, 1944), line 13, <<https://www.philaletheians.co.uk/study-notes/mystic-verse-and-insights/eliot's-four-quartets.pdf>> [accessed 28 October 2024].

² ‘Úhta’, in Joseph Bosworth and T. Northcote Toller, *An Anglo-Saxon Dictionary*, Digital Edition (Prague: Charles University, 2010), <<https://bosworthtoller.com/32479>> [accessed 24 October 2024].

³ Hana Videen, ‘Passing the Time’, in *The Wordhord: Daily Life in Old English* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2022), pp. 42–61 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv2175r86?turn_away=true> [accessed 25 October 2024].

⁴ Dennis Freeborn, *From Old English to Standard English: A Course Book in Language Variation Across Time*, 2nd ed. (Ottawa: University of Ottawa Press/Les Presses de l'Université d'Ottawa, 1998), p.29, <<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/detail.action?docID=4795594>> [accessed 28 October 2024].

⁵ Ibid., p.28.

⁶ Ibid., p.29.

by the figure, the backward arrow in the word indicates a possible earlier usage before OE, and its abrupt cessation around the year 1400 suggests a definitive loss in the English language⁷. Nevertheless, there is still a cognate form in the Modern Dutch word *ochtend* which according to Cambridge Dictionary means ‘the first part of the day, approximately up to noon’⁸. With regard to its semantic evolution, the word seems to have retained its original meaning through to Middle English, particularly within certain specialized contexts, such as those connected to the monastic hour of Matins⁹, which will be further discussed later on.

Figure 1. ‘01.13.05.01.02/01 n. early morning: Timeline Visualization’ from *the Historical Thesaurus of English*.¹⁰

⁷ ‘01.13.05.01.02 / 01 (n.): early morning’, in *The Historical Thesaurus of English*, 2nd ed., version 5.0. (Glasgow: University of Glasgow, 2024) <<https://ht.ac.uk/category/?id=88631>> [accessed 28 October 2024].

⁸ ‘Ochtend’, in *Cambridge Dictionary*, Digital Edition <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/dutch-english/ochtend>> [accessed 12 November 2024]

⁹ ‘03.08.04.06.01 n. Matins’, in *The Historical Thesaurus of English*, <<https://ht.ac.uk/category/#id=178860>> [accessed 28 October 2024].

¹⁰ ‘01.13.05.01.02|01 (n.) early morning: Timeline Visualization’, in *The Historical Thesaurus of English*, <<https://ht.ac.uk/category/#id=88630>> [accessed 28 October 2024].

Regarding semantics, Bosworth-Toller defines it as ‘the time just before daybreak’¹¹. As previously mentioned, this word does not endure in Modern English, but it used to conceptualise a specific moment of the night, the hours before the arrival of the morning. In poetry, it is a very useful expression to capture the time when everything feels bleak and cold, often called ‘the darkness before dawn’. An example of this word can be found in the following passage of *The Wanderer*:

Oft him ānhaga āre gebīdeð,
Metudes miltse, þēah þe hē mōdcearig
geond lagulāde longe sceolde
hrēran mid hondum hrīmcealde sǣ,
wadan wræclāstas. Wyrð bið ful āræd.
Swā cwæð eardstapa, earfeþa gemyndig,
wrāþra wælsleahta, winemæga hryre:
Oft ic sceolde āna **ūhtna** gehwylce
mīne ceare cwīþan.¹²

(Often the wanderer walks alone,/ Waits for mercy, longs for grace,/ Stirs the ice-cold sea with hands and oars—/ Heart-sick, endures an exile’s road—/ A hard traveler. His fate is fixed. / So said the wanderer, old earth-walker,/ His mind choked with the memory of strife,/ Fierce slaughter and the fall of kinsmen:/ Often alone at the **edge of dawn**,/ I must wake to the sound of my own sorrow,)¹³

¹¹ ‘Úhta’, in Bosworth-Toller.

¹² Peter Baker, ed., ‘The Wanderer’, *Old English Aerobics Anthology*, <<https://www.oldenglishaerobics.net/wanderer.php>>, lines 1-9, [accessed 29 October 2024].

¹³ Craig Williamson, trans., ‘The Wanderer’ in *The Complete Old English Poems* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2017), p.456, <<http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/detail.action?docID=4794450>> [accessed 29 October 2024].

In this context, the word helps to create an atmosphere in consonance with the feelings of the poetic voice. The last hours of the night are conducive to reflection and sadness, as the world is still and everyone is asleep. Readers have undoubtedly encountered similar emotions at some point, which enables them to be fully immersed in the protagonist's mind, hearing solely his chain of thoughts, free from any background noise, enveloped in silence. What the wanderer experiences, his anxiety in the hours before dawn, also has a specific name in Old English: *úht-cearu*, 'care that comes in the early morning'¹⁴, compound word made up of *úht*, the strong form of our word, and *cearu* ('care', 'sorrow', 'grief')¹⁵. Furthermore, *úhta* also conveys a sense of coolness characteristic of the early morning hours, reinforcing the absence of warmth or affection experienced by the wanderer, who finds himself isolated after losing his loved ones. This feeling of confronting sorrow and harsh reality is also vividly exemplified in the poem *Beowulf*, when the terror and suffering caused by Grendel become evident during these hours: 'Ða wæs on **uhtan** mid ærdæge/ Grendles guðcraeft gumum undyrne'¹⁶; (When it was **the early hours before daybreak**, with the first light,/Grendel's warlike power was revealed to men) [My own translation].

However, 'there is no certainty as to whether *The Wanderer* was composed by a pagan or a Christian poet, or was even composed by the former and reworked by the latter'¹⁷. Consequently, the word may possess religious connotations in this often-called elegy. In Christianity, light represents God's presence, truth, salvation, spiritual illumination or hope, in contrast to darkness, which signifies sin, separation from God and ignorance. The pre-dawn hours are a time of transition between night and day, light and darkness, and, within a potential religious context, the shift between the absence and presence of the divine. It remains uncertain whether the poem involves multiple speakers or solely the voice of the wanderer, as well as whether its origin was pagan. Nevertheless, the end is clearly Christian when referring directly

¹⁴ 'Úht-cearu' in Bosworth-Toller.

¹⁵ 'Cearu' in Bosworth-Toller.

¹⁶ West Virginia University, *Beowulf: Lines 1 to 228*

<<https://www.as.wvu.edu/english/oeoe/english311/228.html>> [accessed 12 November 2024]

¹⁷ *The Anglo-Saxon World: An Anthology*, ed. by Kevin Crossley-Holland (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 1999), p.47,

<<https://archive.org/details/anglosaxonworlda0000unse/page/n5/mode/1up>>[accessed 10 November 2024].

to his 'Fæder' and as the scholar James H. Wilson stated, everything suggests that, 'on the symbolic-allegorical level the cold and hunger and loneliness are signs of other relevances on different contextual levels'¹⁸.

Besides this symbolism, it should also be mentioned that in medieval Christian tradition, time was structured around the canonical hours, which marked specific moments for prayer and reflection. The time of the *úhta* corresponds to Matins or Vigils, celebrated after midnight, about 2:00 or 3:00 a.m.¹⁹, it was part of a cycle of eight prayer services in the Liturgy of the Hours and they symbolized a moment of spiritual awakening, a preparation for the light of the day, and was traditionally a time of introspection and penitence. In fact, there is a specific word to refer to Matins, the compound *úht-sang* ('one of the services of the church, nocturns or matins')²⁰, which we can observe in texts such as Ælfric's *Colloquy*: 'On þisse niht, þa þa cnyll ic gehyrde, ic aras on minon bedde ond eode to cyrcean, ond sang **uhtsang** mid gebroþrum'²¹; (Last night, when I heard the knell, I arose from my bed and went out to the church, and sang **Nocturn** with my brethren;)²². This also reinforces the idea that *úhta* carries Christian connotations in the poem, suggesting that the wanderer's awakening will not only be a physical one, emerging from a dream, but also a spiritual one, leading him to find the answer in a divine figure. In a manner reminiscent of Eliot's notion that 'the darkness shall be the light', the transition from the cold and desolate darkness of *úhta* to the hopeful promise of dawn

¹⁸ James H. Wilson, *Christian Theology and Old English Poetry* (The Hague: Mouton, 1974), p.85, <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=sqQDDgAAQBAJ&pg=PA3&hl=es&source=gbs_selected_pages&cad=1#v=onepage&q&f=false> [accessed 10 November 2024]

¹⁹ Joanne M. Pierce, 'Medieval Christian Liturgy' in *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Religion*, 9 May 2016
<<https://oxfordre.com/religion/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780199340378.001.0001/acrefore-9780199340378-e-84>> [accessed 10 November 2024].

²⁰ 'Úht-sang' in Bosworth-Toller.

²¹ Ælfric's 'Colloquy', ed. by George N.G. (Exeter: University of Exeter, 1978), p.44.

²² Stephen J. Harris, 'Ælfric's *Colloquy*', in *Medieval Literature for Children*, ed. by Daniel T. Kline (New York: Routledge, 2003), pp. 112-130 (p.125)
<<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/reader.action?docID=1099254&ppg=122>>
[accessed 12 November 2024].

shows the wanderer's movement from a state of despair to a sense of optimism and sacred illumination.

In conclusion, the word *úhta* holds significant complexity in *The Wanderer*. As demonstrated, it not only conveys a sensory image imbued with cold, silence, and solitude, but also represents a metonymic shift in the poet's emotions, from sorrow to comfort. This shift is likely connected to the Christian symbolism of light and darkness, reflecting the religious significance that this term and its derivatives held in Old English texts.

Bibliography

Primary Sources

Baker, Peter, ed., 'The Wanderer', *Old English Aerobics Anthology*,

<<https://www.oldenglishaerobics.net/wanderer.php>> [accessed 29 October 2024]

Eliot, T.S., 'East Coker', in *Four Quarters* (London: Faber and Faber, 1944), line 13,

<<https://www.philaletheians.co.uk/study-notes/mystic-verse-and-insights/eliot's-four-quartets.pdf>>

[accessed 28 October 2024]

J.Harris, Stephen, 'Aelfric's *Colloquy*', in *Medieval Literature for Children*, ed. by Daniel T.Kline (New York: Routledge, 2003), pp. 112-130

N.G., George, ed. *Aelfric's 'Colloquy'* (Exeter: University of Exeter, 1978)

West Virginia University, *Beowulf: Lines 1 to 228*

<<https://www.as.wvu.edu/english/oeoe/english311/228.html>> [accessed 12 November 2024]

Williamson, Craig, trans., 'The Wanderer', in *The Complete Old English Poems* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2017), p.456,

<<http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/detail.action?docID=4794450>> [accessed 29

October 2024]

Secondary sources

Bosworth, Joseph, and T. Northcote Toller, *An Anglo-Saxon Dictionary*, Digital Edition (Prague:

Charles University, 2010), <<http://bosworth.ff.cuni.cz/>> [accessed 24 October 2024]

Cambridge Dictionary, Digital Edition <[https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/dutch-](https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/dutch-english/ochtend)

[english/ochtend](https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/dutch-english/ochtend)> [accessed 12 November 2024]

Crossley-Holland, Kevin, ed., *The Anglo-Saxon World: An Anthology*, Holland (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 1999)

Freeborn, Dennis, *From Old English to Standard English: A Course Book in Language Variation Across Time*, 2nd ed. (Ottawa: University of Ottawa Press/Les Presses de l'Université d'Ottawa, 1998) <<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/detail.action?docID=4795594>> [accessed 28 October 2024]

H. Wilson, James, *Christian Theology and Old English Poetry*, (The Hague: Mouton, 1974)

Pierce, Joanne M., 'Medieval Christian Liturgy' in *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Religion*, 9 May 2016, <<https://oxfordre.com/religion/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780199340378.001.0001/acrefore-9780199340378-e-84>> [accessed 10 November 2024]

The Historical Thesaurus of English, 2nd edn., version 5.0 (Glasgow: University of Glasgow, 2024) <<https://ht.ac.uk/search/>> [accessed 28 October 2024]

Videen, Hana, 'Passing the Time', in *The Wordhord: Daily Life in Old English* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2022), pp. 42–61 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv2175r86?turn_away=true> [accessed 25 October 2024]